

NIBS-BIDS: an extension to the brain imaging data structure for non-invasive brain stimulation

Giacomo Bertazzoli^{1,2,*}, Oleg Shevtsov^{3,†}, Martina Bulgari^{4,‡}, Peter J. Fried^{1,2,‡}, Giacomo Guidali^{5,‡}, Vittorio Iacovella^{6,‡}, Eleonora Marcantoni^{7,‡}, Til Ole Bergmann^{8,9}, Friederike Breuer^{8,9}, Stefanie De Smet¹⁰, Zhi-De Deng¹¹, Matteo Feurra³, Rémi Gau¹², Yaroslav O. Halchenko¹³, Julio C. Hernandez-Pavon¹⁴, Nicholas P. Holmes¹⁵, Amber Hopkins¹⁶, Silvia Isabella^{17,18}, Milana Makarova^{3,19}, Guiomar Niso²⁰, Desmond Oathes^{21,22,23,24}, Giovanni Pellegrino²⁵, Natalie Rotstein²⁶, Victor H. Souza^{27,28}, Suhas Vijayakumar⁸, Mikkel C. Vinding^{29,30}, Taylor Kuhn²⁶, Marta Bortoletto^{31,§}, Nigel Rogasch^{32,33,34,§}

The Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) is a community standard for organizing and sharing neuroimaging data. Here we present NIBS-BIDS (BEP037), an extension of BIDS for non-invasive brain stimulation (NIBS) data. This specification introduces a dedicated *nibs/* datatype with a scalable framework for storing stimulation parameters, modality-specific device metadata, spatial targeting information, and event-level synchronization for transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS), transcranial electrical stimulation (tES), and transcranial ultrasound stimulation (TUS). We describe the proposed data structure, its design rationale, and its intended role in facilitating reproducible NIBS research.

Affiliations

¹ Berenson-Allen Center for Noninvasive Brain Stimulation, Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center and Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA, USA

² Department of Neurology, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA, USA

³ Centre for Cognition and Decision Making, Institute for Cognitive Neuroscience, HSE University, Moscow, Russian Federation

⁴ School of Medicine and Surgery, University of Milano-Bicocca, Milano, Italy

⁵ Department of Psychology and Milan Center for Neuroscience – NeuroMI, University of Milano-Bicocca, Milano, Italy

⁶ Center for Mind/Brain Sciences – CIMeC, University of Trento, Trento, Italy

⁷ Centre for Neurotechnology, School of Psychology and Neuroscience, University of Glasgow, Glasgow, UK

⁸ Neuroimaging Center (NIC), Focus Programme Translational Neuroscience (FTN), Johannes Gutenberg University Medical Center, Mainz, Germany

⁹ Leibniz Institute for Resilience Research (LIR), Mainz, Germany

¹⁰ Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

¹¹ National Institute of Mental Health, NIH, Bethesda, MD, USA

¹² BIDS Maintainer Team

¹³ Center for Open Neuroscience, Department of Psychological and Brain Sciences, Dartmouth College, Hanover, NH, USA

¹⁴ Department of Psychological Sciences, Kansas State University, Manhattan, KS, USA

¹⁵ School of Sport, Exercise and Rehabilitation Sciences, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, UK

¹⁶ University of California Los Angeles, Los Angeles, CA, USA

¹⁷ Baycrest Academy for Research and Education, Toronto, ON, Canada

¹⁸ Campus Bio-Medico University of Rome, Rome, Italy

¹⁹ Medical Computer Systems Ltd., Zelenograd, Russian Federation

- ²⁰ Cajal Neuroscience Center, CSIC, Madrid, Spain
- ²¹ Center for Brain Imaging and Stimulation, Department of Psychiatry, University of Pennsylvania Perelman School of Medicine, Philadelphia, PA, USA
- ²² Departments of Neuroscience, Bioengineering, Neurology and Neurosurgery, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, PA, USA
- ²³ Center for Neuromodulation in Depression and Stress, University of Pennsylvania Perelman School of Medicine, Philadelphia, PA, USA
- ²⁴ Penn Brain Science, Translation, Innovation, and Modulation Center, University of Pennsylvania Perelman School of Medicine, Philadelphia, PA, USA
- ²⁵ Clinical Neurological Sciences, Schulich School of Medicine, Western University, London, ON, Canada
- ²⁶ Department of Psychiatry and Biobehavioral Sciences, University of California Los Angeles, Los Angeles, CA, USA
- ²⁷ Department of Neuroscience and Biomedical Engineering, School of Science, Aalto University, Espoo, Finland
- ²⁸ Cortisys Ltd, Espoo, Finland
- ²⁹ Department of Psychology, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark
- ³⁰ Department of Clinical Neuroscience, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden
- ³¹ MoMi Lab, IMT School for Advanced Studies, Lucca, Italy
- ³² School of Pharmacy and Biomedical Sciences, College of Health, Adelaide University, Adelaide, Australia
- ³³ Hopwood Centre for Neurobiology, Lifelong Health Theme, South Australian Health and Medical Research Institute (SAHMRI), Adelaide, Australia
- ³⁴ School of Psychological Sciences and Turner Institute for Brain and Mental Health, Monash University, Melbourne, Australia

* First author; † Co-first author; ‡ Lead contributors; § Co-last and last author

Correspondence: gbertazz@bidmc.harvard.edu

Introduction

Non-invasive brain stimulation (NIBS) encompasses a family of techniques that modulate neuronal activity through the intact skull and scalp^{1,2}. The three principal modalities are transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS), which uses brief magnetic pulses to induce electric currents in conductive tissue³⁻⁵; transcranial electrical stimulation (tES), which delivers low-amplitude currents via scalp electrodes (including variants such as transcranial direct current stimulation [tDCS], transcranial alternating current stimulation [tACS], and transcranial random noise stimulation [tRNS])^{1,6,7}; and transcranial ultrasound stimulation (TUS), which focuses acoustic energy to modulate neuronal activity^{8,9}. These techniques are widely used in cognitive neuroscience to investigate brain-behaviour relationships^{10,11} and, in clinical practice, are receiving progressive regulatory approval for therapeutic use^{12,13}, with indications spanning major depressive disorder¹⁴⁻¹⁶, obsessive-compulsive disorder^{17,18}, and movement disorders^{19,20}.

Despite the growing importance of NIBS in both research and clinical settings, no community standard currently exists for organizing, documenting, and sharing stimulation data. Each laboratory stores NIBS parameters in idiosyncratic formats often with inconsistent or missing metadata, making it difficult for independent teams to reproduce published protocols, pool datasets, or conduct meta-analyses²¹⁻²³. This stands in contrast to other areas of neuroscience, where the adoption of common data structures has enabled large-scale analyses that were previously impossible²⁴⁻²⁶.

The Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS), originally proposed for MRI data²⁵, is a widely adopted community standard for organizing and sharing brain imaging study data²⁴ (Figure 1). BIDS has since been extended to EEG²⁷, MEG²⁸, intracranial EEG²⁹, PET³⁰, near-infrared spectroscopy³¹, microscopy³², motion capture³³, and is currently being expanded for EMG (BEP042) among other modalities. BIDS addresses heterogeneity in data organization by following the FAIR principles³⁴ of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

Here we present NIBS-BIDS, a BIDS extension (BEP037) for non-invasive brain stimulation. NIBS-BIDS introduces a dedicated *nibs/* datatype that stores stimulation protocol parameters, spatial targeting coordinates, modality-specific device metadata, and event-level synchronization information in a scalable framework. The specification provides modality-specific support for TMS, tES, and TUS, each with tailored device descriptions, spatial representations, and parameter sets. Because NIBS-BIDS operates within the broader BIDS ecosystem, stimulation metadata can be directly linked to concurrent recording modalities already supported or under development in BIDS, such as EMG, EEG, MRI, and fNIRS, through the shared framework. In this document, we describe the main features of the NIBS-BIDS specification. The full development repository is available at (<https://github.com/nigelrogasch/nibs-bids/>).

NIBS-BIDS specification

The NIBS-BIDS extension introduces a dedicated *nibs/* directory as a standalone datatype, analogous to *eeg/*, *pet/*, or *motion/* (see Figure 2). Each subject's stimulation data are stored in a *nibs/* subdirectory

containing several core file types that together describe what stimulation was performed, how it was configured, and its target location. The primary tabular file, `_nibs.tsv`, records one row per stimulation event. A stimulation event is defined as one delivery of stimulation initiated by a single command, such as a single pulse, a paired-pulse sequence, or a device-programmed train. For modalities involving multiple contacts or channels (e.g., tES montages or phased-array TUS), a single event may span multiple rows sharing the same `event_id`, indexed by `event_part`. Each row captures per-event values, such as stimulation intensity, threshold parameters, spatial target references, and timing information.

An accompanying sidecar, `_nibs.json`, provides structured metadata about the stimulation device, task context, and reusable configuration definitions organized into two layers. The **device layer** contains modality-specific hardware blocks: **CoilSet** for TMS coils, **ElectrodeSet** for tES electrode/contact hardware (including electrode role, shape, area, and material), and **TransducerSet** for TUS transducers (including focusing characteristics, carrier frequency, and phased-array extensions). The **stimulus layer** contains **StimulusSet**, which defines reusable stimulation

configurations. For TMS, this includes pulse count, waveform, within-instance timing, and intensity scaling rules. For tES, it captures waveform type, frequency, control mode, and noise parameters (for tRNS). For TUS, it covers continuous, pulsed, and burst protocols, amplitude modulation, and phased-array beamforming parameters.

Spatial information is stored in **_markers.tsv*, where each row represents one spatial point or contact with a unique *target_id*. Rows may include 3D coordinates, standardized location labels (e.g., 10-20 positions), or both, depending on the available targeting information. An optional *target_group* field allows related points to be grouped for organizational purposes (e.g., a tES montage, a multi-coil setup, or a multi-focus TUS protocol), but this field is not used for linkage or synchronization. This file serves a role analogous to **_electrodes.tsv* in EEG-BIDS⁶, but extends it to capture the full spatial specification required for each stimulation modality: coil pose and orientation vectors for TMS, scalp-surface electrode positions for tES, and target/entry/transducer coordinates with beam direction vectors for TUS. The coordinate system is defined in an accompanying **_coordsystem.json* file.

Synchronization with concurrent recording modalities is achieved through **_events.tsv* using the *event_id* field, which links time-stamped annotations to the corresponding stimulation records in **_nibs.tsv*. This design keeps temporal information within the standard BIDS events framework while allowing stimulation-specific detail to reside in the dedicated NIBS files. Optional files for digitized headshape data (**_headshape.pos*) and photographs of anatomical landmarks or fiducials (**_photo.jpg*, **_photo.png*, or **_photo.tif*) are also supported.

Specific NIBS-BIDS Considerations

Several design decisions distinguish the NIBS-BIDS specification from other BIDS modalities.

A single experimental session may involve multiple stimulation modalities (e.g., TMS and tES). NIBS-BIDS introduces the *stimsys-<label>* filename entity to distinguish between stimulation systems. This entity is analogous to *tracksys* in the BIDS motion specification³³ and takes values such as *tms*, *tes*, or *tus*. When *stimsys* is present in a filename, the corresponding sidecar JSON must include a *StimulationSystem* field, and the mapping must be consistent across subjects and sessions within a dataset.

Each NIBS modality uses distinct physical hardware and produces distinct stimulation patterns. The proposed specification captures this through modality-specific device identifier fields in **_nibs.tsv* (*coil_id* for TMS, *electrode_id* for tES, *transducer_id* for TUS) and corresponding hardware definition blocks in **_nibs.json* (*CoilSet*, *ElectrodeSet*, *TransducerSet*). Device identifiers describe physical hardware, not stimulation parameters. Changes in protocol do not require a new device identifier unless the physical hardware itself changes. Similarly, the *StimulusSet* block provides modality-tailored stimulus configuration definitions: pulse-based templates for TMS, waveform/frequency/noise definitions for tES, and continuous/pulsed/burst configurations with optional amplitude modulation and beamforming parameters for TUS.

NIBS experiments vary widely in complexity. The specification accommodates this range in two ways. First, it separates event-specific parameters (e.g., stimulation intensity or timing) from reusable definitions (e.g., device hardware configuration or stimulus protocol templates). The tabular file **_nibs.tsv* uses device identifiers to reference hardware definitions, *stim_id* to reference stimulus configuration templates in *StimulusSet*, and *target_id* to reference spatial target definitions in **_markers.tsv*. This separation keeps the tabular files compact while supporting complex protocols. Second, most fields beyond a minimal core are set to recommended or optional rather than required, so that datasets ranging from a simple single-pulse TMS experiment to a multi-session phased-array TUS

protocol can all be represented without imposing unnecessary burden on researchers with simpler designs.

In **_markers.tsv*, each row represents one spatial point or contact with a unique *target_id*. Multi-point constructs (e.g., tES montages with multiple electrodes, multi-coil TMS setups, or phased-array TUS protocols with multiple focus locations) are represented as multiple rows, each with its own *target_id*. An optional *target_group* field may be used to group related points for organizational purposes, but all linkage from **_nibs.tsv* is performed via *target_id*.

Some stimulation events involve multiple simultaneous contacts or focus points. For example, a tES montage may involve an anode and multiple return electrodes each with its own intensity, a dual-site TMS protocol may deliver stimulation through two coils at different locations, or a phased-array TUS system may steer the beam across multiple focus locations within a single event. In such cases, multiple rows in **_nibs.tsv* share the same *event_id* and are indexed by *event_part*. Each row references its own device identifier, stimulus configuration, and spatial target. For TUS with dynamic beam steering, the *FocusSequence* field in *StimulusSet* defines the order in which focus points (referenced by *event_part*) are stimulated within a single logical event.

Embedding stimulation coordinates, device specifications, and configuration parameters directly in the dataset enables integration with electric- and acoustic-field simulation tools such as SimNIBS¹³. NIBS-BIDS datasets could serve as inputs for computational dose reconstruction without requiring supplementary documentation. Electric field values reported by navigation systems or derived from models may be stored in **_nibs.tsv* along with metadata fields for units, model name, and version, providing provenance for these derived quantities.

Community Tools and Software Support

Upon incorporation into the BIDS standard, datasets formatted to follow the NIBS-BIDS specification may be validated using the BIDS Validator (<https://bids-standard.github.io/bids-validator/>). The BIDS starter kit (<https://github.com/bids-standard/bids-starter-kit>) provides additional community-driven resources for researchers adopting the BIDS framework. NIBS-BIDS has been developed in collaboration with several international consortia, including the Team for TMS-EEG (T4TE³⁵; <https://www.t4te.org/>), the BigNIBS Data initiative^{36,37} (<https://bignibsdata.com/>), the ENIGMA Neuromodulation working group³⁸ (<https://enigma.ini.usc.edu/ongoing/enigma-neuromodulation/>), and BRAIN Initiative EMBER Archive (<https://emberarchive.org>). These collaborations have helped ensure that the proposed specification addresses the practical needs of large-scale, multi-site NIBS research and is compatible with the metadata requirements of ongoing pooled analyses and harmonization efforts.

Future Directions

The NIBS-BIDS addresses the organization and documentation of raw NIBS stimulation data. Several directions for further development are anticipated. First, a pull request incorporating the NIBS-BIDS schema into the main BIDS specification will be opened, enabling schema-based validation of NIBS datasets through the BIDS Validator prior to formal release. Example datasets will be made available through the BIDS-examples repository (<https://github.com/bids-standard/bids-examples>). Second, BIDS derivatives for NIBS, including processed stimulation data, computed electric and acoustic field maps, and derived dose metrics, will enable the sharing of analysis outputs alongside raw data. Third, the development of automated conversion tools and BIDS Apps for NIBS data processing will lower the barrier to adoption and facilitate reproducible analysis pipelines. On its own, NIBS-BIDS represents

a necessary first step toward standardized, reproducible documentation of non-invasive brain stimulation experiments.

Finally, NIBS-BIDS in its present form covers the three principal stimulation modalities—TMS, tES, and TUS, and is designed to accommodate the full range of protocol complexity encountered in current practice. It does not yet address other techniques used in the field, e.g. transcutaneous vagus nerve stimulation (tVNS), or highly non-standard or investigational devices that may not map cleanly onto the current metadata schema. Such modalities have distinct stimulation protocols and hardware configurations that would require dedicated specification work, and their inclusion is deferred to future community-agreed extension efforts.

References

1. Rossini, P. M. *et al.* Non-invasive electrical and magnetic stimulation of the brain, spinal cord, roots and peripheral nerves: Basic principles and procedures for routine clinical and research application: An updated report from an I.F.C.N. Committee. *Clinical Neurophysiology* **126**, 1071–1107 (2015).
2. Hallett, M. Transcranial magnetic stimulation and the human brain. *Nature* **406**, 147–150 (2000).
3. Hallett, M. Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation: A Primer. *Neuron* **55**, 187–199 (2007).
4. Barker, A. T., Jalinous, R. & Freeston, I. L. Non-invasive magnetic stimulation of human motor cortex. *Lancet (London, England)* **1**, 1106–1107 (1985).
5. Rossi, S. *et al.* Safety and recommendations for TMS use in healthy subjects and patient populations, with updates on training, ethical and regulatory issues: Expert Guidelines. *Clin Neurophysiol* **132**, 269–306 (2021).
6. Woods, A. J. *et al.* A technical guide to tDCS, and related non-invasive brain stimulation tools. *Clinical Neurophysiology* **127**, 1031–1048 (2016).
7. Nitsche, M. A. & Paulus, W. Excitability changes induced in the human motor cortex by weak transcranial direct current stimulation. *The Journal of Physiology* **527**, 633–639 (2000).
8. Murphy, K. R. *et al.* A practical guide to transcranial ultrasonic stimulation from the IFCN-endorsed ITRUSST consortium. *Clinical Neurophysiology* **171**, 192–226 (2025).
9. Osada, T. & Konishi, S. Noninvasive intervention by transcranial ultrasound stimulation: Modulation of neural circuits and its clinical perspectives. *Psychiatry Clin Neurosci* **78**, 273–281 (2024).
10. Miniussi, C., Harris, J. A. & Ruzzoli, M. Modelling non-invasive brain stimulation in cognitive neuroscience. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews* **37**, 1702–1712 (2013).
11. Parkin, B. L., Ekhtiari, H. & Walsh, V. F. Non-invasive Human Brain Stimulation in Cognitive Neuroscience: A Primer. *Neuron* **87**, 932–945 (2015).
12. Cohen, S. L., Bikson, M., Badran, B. W. & George, M. S. A visual and narrative timeline of US FDA milestones for Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) devices. *Brain Stimulation* **15**, 73–75 (2022).
13. Kang, J. *et al.* Effects and safety of transcranial direct current stimulation on multiple health outcomes: an umbrella review of randomized clinical trials. *Mol Psychiatry* **29**, 3789–3801 (2024).
14. Trapp, N. T. *et al.* Consensus review and considerations on TMS to treat depression: A comprehensive update endorsed by the National Network of Depression Centers, the Clinical TMS Society, and the International Federation of Clinical Neurophysiology. *Clinical Neurophysiology* **170**, 206–233 (2025).
15. Fregni, F. *et al.* Evidence-Based Guidelines and Secondary Meta-Analysis for the Use of Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation in Neurological and Psychiatric Disorders. *International Journal of Neuropsychopharmacology* **24**, 256–313 (2021).
16. Lefaucheur, J.-P. *et al.* Evidence-based guidelines on the therapeutic use of repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation (rTMS): An update (2014–2018). *Clinical Neurophysiology* **131**, 474–528 (2020).
17. Grassi, G., Moradei, C. & Cecchelli, C. Will Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation Improve the Treatment of Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder? A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Current Targets and Clinical Evidence. *Life (Basel)* **13**, 1494 (2023).
18. Carmi, L. *et al.* Efficacy and Safety of Deep Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation for Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder: A Prospective Multicenter Randomized Double-Blind Placebo-Controlled Trial. *AJP* **176**, 931–938 (2019).
19. Conte, D. *et al.* The effects of transcranial magnetic stimulation in motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease: an overview of systematic reviews with meta-analysis. *Neurol Sci* **46**, 3405–3418 (2025).
20. Latorre, A., Rocchi, L., Berardelli, A., Bhatia, K. P. & Rothwell, J. C. The use of transcranial magnetic stimulation as a treatment for movement disorders: A critical review. *Movement Disorders* **34**, 769–782 (2019).

21. Peterchev, A. V. *et al.* Fundamentals of transcranial electric and magnetic stimulation dose: Definition, selection, and reporting practices. *Brain Stimulation* **5**, 435–453 (2012).
22. Héroux, M. E., Loo, C. K., Taylor, J. L. & Gandevia, S. C. Questionable science and reproducibility in electrical brain stimulation research. *PLoS ONE* **12**, e0175635 (2017).
23. Chipchase, L. *et al.* A checklist for assessing the methodological quality of studies using transcranial magnetic stimulation to study the motor system: An international consensus study. *Clinical Neurophysiology* **123**, 1698–1704 (2012).
24. Poldrack, R. A. *et al.* The Past, Present, and Future of the Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS). Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2309.05768> (2024).
25. Gorgolewski, K. J. *et al.* The brain imaging data structure, a format for organizing and describing outputs of neuroimaging experiments. *Scientific Data* **2016 3:1 3**, 1–9 (2016).
26. Markiewicz, C. J. *et al.* The OpenNeuro resource for sharing of neuroscience data. *eLife* **10**, e71774 (2021).
27. Pernet, C. R. *et al.* EEG-BIDS, an extension to the brain imaging data structure for electroencephalography. *Scientific Data* **6**, 1–5 (2019).
28. Niso, G. *et al.* MEG-BIDS, the brain imaging data structure extended to magnetoencephalography. *Scientific Data* **2018 5:1 5**, 1–5 (2018).
29. Holdgraf, C. *et al.* iEEG-BIDS, extending the Brain Imaging Data Structure specification to human intracranial electrophysiology. *Scientific Data* **6**, (2019).
30. Norgaard, M. *et al.* PET-BIDS, an extension to the brain imaging data structure for positron emission tomography. *Scientific Data* **9**, 1–7 (2022).
31. Luke, R. *et al.* NIRS-BIDS: Brain Imaging Data Structure Extended to Near-Infrared Spectroscopy. *Sci Data* **12**, 159 (2025).
32. Bourget, M.-H. *et al.* Microscopy-BIDS: An Extension to the Brain Imaging Data Structure for Microscopy Data. *Front. Neurosci.* **16**, 871228 (2022).
33. Jeung, S. *et al.* Motion-BIDS: an extension to the brain imaging data structure to organize motion data for reproducible research. *Sci Data* **11**, 716 (2024).
34. Wilkinson, M. D. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016).
35. Bortoletto, M. *et al.* T4TE: Team for TMS–EEG and improve reproducibility through an open collaborative initiative. *Brain Stimulation: Basic, Translational, and Clinical Research in Neuromodulation* <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BRS.2022.12.004> (2022) doi:10.1016/J.BRS.2022.12.004.
36. Corp, D. T. *et al.* Big non-invasive brain stimulation data (Big NIBS data): An open-access platform and repository for NIBS data. *Brain Stimulation* **18**, 278–279 (2025).
37. Corp, D. T. *et al.* Large-scale analysis of interindividual variability in theta-burst stimulation data: Results from the ‘Big TMS Data Collaboration’. *Brain Stimulation* **13**, 1476–1488 (2020).
38. Kuhn, T. *et al.* The ENIGMA Neuromodulation Working Group: Goals, Challenges, and Opportunities for the Field. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/cuxkz> (2024).

Acknowledgements

We thank the members of the BIDS community for their feedback and discussions during the development of this extension proposal. We acknowledge the collaborative contributions of the T4TE, and the BigNIBS Data initiative the ENIGMA Neuromodulation working group. Work of YOH was supported by EMBER (NIH R24MH136632, R24DA064430) project.

Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests

Data Availability

The archive of the NIBS-BIDS specification proposal versions is available at <https://github.com/nigelrogasch/nibs-bids/> and up-to-date information about BEP037 can be found at https://bids.neuroimaging.io/extensions/beps/bep_037.html. The BIDS project website is at <https://bids.neuroimaging.io/>.